

Preparation and Characterisation of some Oxomolybdenum(V) Complexes using 2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzthiazole

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In course of the detailed investigation on the chemistry of different 'oxo-ion complexes' of the transitional metals, it was noted by the present authors that the chemical and magneto-optic behaviour of certain oxo-ions do not fully depend upon the point group and molecular orbital picture of the oxo-ion 'moiety' especially in solution and more precisely in aqueous solution. In the case of vanadium, chromium and molybdenum, the oxo-ions VO^{2+} , CrO^{3+} and MoO^{3+} all are d^1 -systems having C_{4v} symmetry in oxopentahalo-complexes behave entirely in a different manner in aqueous solution¹. In case of MoO^{3+} smooth and kinetically slow hydrolysis and elimination of oxo-bridge and hence resulting in diamagnetic compounds.

In the present communication, synthesis and characterisation of oxomolybdenum(V) compounds using 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole (PBT) (Fig. 1) as the metal binding substrate containing interesting donor sites ($-\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$) similar to 2, 2'-bipyridyl and 1, 10-phenanthroline have been achieved and the interesting species have been studied and characterised by different physicochemical methods.

Fig. 1

Results and Discussion

The salt oxopentabromomolybdate(V) with the titled ligand was obtained as brown coloured microcrystalline solid. The compound is sufficiently stable

at room temperature. However, it begins to eliminate hydrogen bromide when stored for long time in the vacuum desiccator over solid KOH and the colour is also changed from brown to reddish brown. This is a clear indication for strong affinity of MoO^{3+} moiety for the ligand ultimately forming a red coloured non-electrolyte $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{PBT}]$.

This dehydrohalogenation reaction was carried out in solution by refluxing the parent salt with different solvents like absolute ethanol, acetonitrile and acetylacetone yielding $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{PBT}]$ with same chemical composition but different colours, i.e. violet and red. The difference in colour may be due to stereoisomers *cis* and *trans* forms as suggested by previous authors in the identical cases². Due to identical morphology, distinction from spectral point of view is not very sharp. Even dipole moment measurement is not possible due to insolubility of the complexes in non-polar solvents. The violet form is more susceptible towards hydrolysis leading to formation of acidic solution. However, in contrast, the red form is almost unaffected by water. It is clear from the observation that when chlorine is substituted by bromine in *trans* position (*trans* to oxygen of $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$) the dehydrohalogenation becomes fast and easier than chlorine perhaps due to strong *trans* effect. Low electrostatic interaction of the $\text{Mo}-\text{Br}$ bond in $\text{M}=\text{Mo}-\text{Br}$ species is clearly reflected by red and blue shift in the electronic spectra of MoOBr_5^{2-} species². The λ_{max} values for the ligands are 550 and 512 nm and those for the MoOBr_5^{2-} species² are 695, 469, 412, 375, 285 and 249 nm.

The molar conductance value for the salt is $119 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$, the value compatible with 1 : 1 electrolyte³, and for the non-electrolytes the values range from 9.52 to

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl no.	Compd	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Oxidation state of Mo	Molar cond. $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2$	μ_{eff}^* B.M	$\langle g \rangle$	$\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ cm^{-1}
		Mo	N	Br					
1	PBTH ₂ [MoOBr ₅]	13.38 (13.21)	3.52 (3.85)	55.14 (55.10)	4.89	119	1.66 (299)	1.91	985
2. (a)	[MoOBr ₃ .PBT] Violet from ethanol	17.34 (17.02)	4.72 (4.96)	42.69 (42.55)	4.93	9.52	1.69 (303)	1.90	960
(b)	[MoOBr ₃ .PBT] Red from acetonitrile	17.29 (17.02)	4.80 (4.96)	42.41 (42.55)	4.99	10.57	1.70 (303)	1.89	965
	[MoOBr ₃ .PBT] from acetylacetone	17.19 (17.02)	4.76 (4.96)	42.69 (42.55)	4.95	11.89	1.69 (303)	1.89	960
3.	[Mo ₂ O ₃ Br ₄ (PBT) ₂]	19.13 (19.50)	5.21 (5.69)	31.97 (32.52)	5.11	14.64	1.32 (301)		950, 750, 720
4.	[Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₂ (PBT) ₂]	23.47 (22.84)	6.21 (6.66)	19.13 (19.05)	5.00	17.30			950, 750, 720

*Value in parentheses indicates the temperature (K) of measurement.

17.30 $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2$ which are much less than the binary electrolytes (Table 1). The room temperature magnetic moments of the salt and its mono-oxo derivatives after incorporating diamagnetic correction are found to be in the range 1.66–1.70 B.M., which confirms the presence of MoO³⁺ unit in these compounds with *d*¹-configuration of molybdenum. The diamagnetic behaviour of [Mo₂O₄Br₂(PBT)₂] is expected due to presence of Mo₂O₄²⁺ moiety. However, reduced paramagnetism has been observed for [Mo₂O₃Br₄(PBT)₂] (1.21 B.M.) which is expected for this specimen⁴. From epr spectra the average $\langle g \rangle$ values were calculated and these values also support the *d*¹-configuration of oxometal ion. The epr spectrum of the salt PBTH₂[MoOBr₅] is given in Fig. 2. The ir spectra of the complexes exhibit strong absorptions at 960 (deep violet) and 950 cm^{-1} (red) which are diagnostic in deciding the symmetric stretching mode of the terminal Mo=O band⁵. The bands at 720–750 cm^{-1} are assignable to Mo–O–Mo vibration⁶. The pyridine ring breathing mode of the free ligand (990 cm^{-1}) raised to higher frequencies in the complexes, suggests coordination of pyridine nitrogen to the metal ion⁷. The electronic spectral bands of the complexes are in fairly good agreement with those of the similar types of com-

Fig. 2. Epr spectrum of powdered 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazoliumoxopentabromomolybdate(V), PBTH₂[MoOBr₅] at room temperature.

pounds having octahedral geometry⁸. Electronic spectral data for the complexes [MoOBr₃.PBT] and their probable assignments are presented in the Table 2.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by a modified method of Rao and Walhgren⁹. Here the condensation of pyridine-2-carboxylic acid with *o*-aminophenol was performed more conveniently in hot orthophosphoric acid medium.

TABLE 2 – ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES
 [MoOBr₃.PBT]

Compd.	λ_{\max} nm	ϵ	Assignment	
[MoOBr ₃ .PBT]	716	90	$2B_2 \rightarrow 2E$	(I)
Violet	442	1 340	$2B_2 \rightarrow 2B_1$	
	362	82 000	L \rightarrow Mo	
			Charge transfer	
	290	9 500	$2B_2 \rightarrow 2B_2$	(II)
	240	9 000	$2B_2 \rightarrow 2E$	(III)
[MoOBr ₃ .PBT]	710	80	$2B_2 \rightarrow 2E$	(I)
Red	445	1 140	$2B_2 \rightarrow 2B_1$	
	366	3 500	L \rightarrow Mo	
			Charge transfer	
	305	6 400	$2B_2 \rightarrow 2B_2$	(II)
	242	5 800	$2B_2 \rightarrow 2E$	(III)

Molybdenum and bromine were estimated gravimetrically by standard method as oxinate¹⁰ and silver bromide respectively. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method. The oxidation state was determined by ceric sulphate method. Molar conductivity of the complexes was measured in acetonitrile using a Dip type cell. The magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Guoy balance at room temperature. Epr spectra were recorded on E-112 spectrometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (acetonitrile) on a Perkin-Elmer 550S spectrophotometer.

2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzthiazolium-oxopentabromomolybdate(V), $PBTH_2[MoOBr_5]$: Molybdenum trioxide (1.0 g) was gently boiled with concentrated hydrobromic acid (9 N; 10 ml) and evaporated almost to dryness to drive off the liberated bromine. The moist solid was then dissolved in fresh hydrobromic acid (10 ml) with slight warming when a brown solution was obtained. To this solution the ligand (1.5 g), previously dissolved in minimum quantity of the same acid, was added and stirred well. A brown coloured compound that separated out on cooling was washed with hydrobromic acid and dried in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, (yield \sim 1.5 g).

Oxotribromo[2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole]molybdenum(V), $[MoOBr_3.PBT]$: Deep violet variety: The parent salt $PBTH_2[MoOBr_5]$ (1 g) was refluxed with absolute ethanol (20 ml) for 1 h, when dehydrohalogenation took place and the deep violet coloured compound formed on cooling, was dried under reduced pressure (\sim 0.82 g).

Red variety: The compounds with identical composition as the red colour variety were prepared by refluxing the parent salt (1 g) in acetonitrile (20 ml) and acetylacetone (20 ml) for 1.5 h respectively. In the previous case, the yield was 0.76 g and in the later 0.7 g.

Oxo- μ -tetrabromobis-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole-molybdenum(V), $[Mo_2O_3Br_4.(PBT)_2]$: The salt $PBTH_2[MoOBr_5]$ (1 g) was refluxed with ethanol-water mixture (1 : 1) for 1 h. The brick-red coloured compound obtained on cooling, was washed with water-ethanol mixture and dried under reduced pressure (\sim 0.69 g).

Oxo- μ -dioxobromobis-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole-molybdenum(V), $[Mo_2O_4Br_2.(PBT)_2]$: The salt $PBTH_2[MoOBr_5]$ (1 g) was gently boiled with distilled water (15 ml) for 15 min. The deep red coloured compound obtained on cooling, was washed twice with cold water and dried under reduced pressure (\sim 0.79 g).

Analytical and physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

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